

Evaluation of high-resolution predictions of fine particulate matter and its composition in an urban area using PMCAMx-v2.0

Brian T. Dinkelacker¹, Pablo Garcia Rivera¹, Ioannis Kioutsioukis², Peter J. Adams^{3,4}, Spyros N. Pandis^{5,6}

¹*Department of Chemical Engineering, Carnegie Mellon University, Pittsburgh, PA 15213, USA*

²*Department of Physics, University of Patras, 26500, Patras, Greece*

³*Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Carnegie Mellon University, Pittsburgh, PA 15213, USA*

⁴*Department of Engineering and Public Policy, Carnegie Mellon University, Pittsburgh, PA 15213, USA*

⁵*Institute of Chemical Engineering Sciences (FORTH/ICE-HT), 26504, Patras, Greece*

⁶*Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Patras, 26500, Patras, Greece*

*Correspondence to: Spyros N. Pandis (spyros@chemeng.upatras.gr)

Abstract

Accurately predicting urban PM_{2.5} concentrations and composition has proved challenging in the past, partially due to the resolution limitations of computationally intensive chemical transport models (CTMs). Increasing the resolution of PM_{2.5} predictions is desired to support emissions control policy development and address issues related to environmental justice. A nested grid approach using the CTM PMCAMx-v2.0 was used to predict PM_{2.5} at increasing resolutions of 36 x 36, 12 x 12, 4 x 4, and 1 x 1 km for a domain largely consisting of Allegheny County and the city of Pittsburgh in southwestern Pennsylvania, US during February and July 2017. Performance of the model in reproducing PM_{2.5} concentrations and composition was evaluated at the finest scale using measurements from regulatory sites as well as a network of low-cost monitors. Novel surrogates were developed to allocate emissions from cooking and on-road traffic sources to the 1 x 1 km resolution grid. Total PM_{2.5} mass is reproduced well by the model during the winter period with low fractional error (0.3) and fractional bias (+0.05) when compared to regulatory measurements. Comparison with speciated measurements during this period identified small underpredictions of PM_{2.5} sulfate, elemental carbon (EC), and organic aerosol (OA) offset by a larger overprediction of PM_{2.5} nitrate. In the summer period, total PM_{2.5} mass is underpredicted due to a large underprediction of OA (bias = -1.9 μg m⁻³, fractional bias

37 = -0.41). In the winter period, the model performs well reproducing the variability between
38 urban measurements and rural measurements of local pollutants such as EC and OA. This
39 effect is less consistent in the summer period due to a larger fraction of long range transport
40 OA. Comparison with total PM_{2.5} concentration measurements from low-cost sensors
41 showed improvements in performance with increasing resolution. Inconsistencies in PM_{2.5}
42 nitrate predictions in both periods are believed to be due to errors in partitioning between
43 PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ modes and motivate improvements to the treatment of dust particles within
44 the model. The underprediction of summer OA would likely be improved by updates to
45 biogenic SOA chemistry within the model, which would result in an increase of long-range
46 transport SOA seen in the inner modeling domain. These improvements are obvious topics
47 for future work towards model improvement. Comparison with regulatory monitors
48 showed that increasing resolution from 36 km to 1 km improved both fractional error and
49 fractional bias in both modeling periods. Improvements at all types of measurement
50 locations indicated an improved ability of the model to reproduce urban-rural PM_{2.5}
51 gradients at higher resolutions.

52

53 **1 Introduction**

54 Fine particulate matter with aerodynamic diameter less than 2.5 μm (PM_{2.5}) has
55 been associated with public health concerns due to short and long-term exposure. Some of
56 the health effects of PM_{2.5} include increased risk of heart disease, increased likelihood of
57 heart attacks and strokes, impaired lung development, and increased risk of lung disease
58 (Dockery and Pope, 1994). Chemical transport models are frequently used for supporting
59 the development of air quality policies designed to protect public health. To evaluate these
60 policies, CTMs must simulate PM_{2.5} concentrations and their response to changes in
61 emissions accurately.

62 Grid resolution is an important factor for CTM studies focusing on major urban
63 areas since on-road traffic, commercial cooking, and biomass burning can have sharp
64 gradients at the urban scale (Lanz et al., 2007; Allan et al., 2010). High spatial resolution
65 measurements of PM₁ in the city of Pittsburgh in high source-impact locations are on
66 average 40% higher than at urban background locations (Gu et al., 2018). Heightened
67 organic aerosol concentrations have been observed in commercial districts containing

68 multiple restaurants (Robinson et al., 2018). The demographic characteristics of the
69 population can also have large variations at the neighborhood scale. High resolution
70 predictions of pollutant concentrations allow for exposure assessments that compare
71 subpopulations within the same metropolitan area to answer environmental justice related
72 questions (Anand, 2002). The benefits of high-resolution modeling must be balanced with
73 the increased complexity in the development of accurate, high-resolution emission
74 inventories and increased computational cost and storage requirements.

75 Previous studies have found small to modest improvements on the predictive ability
76 of regional CTMs for ozone in the summers of 1995, 1996, and 1997 moving from 36 km
77 to 12 km resolution (Arunachalam et al., 2006) as well as in July 1988 using a dynamic
78 grid system with sizes varying from 18.5 km to 4.625 km (Kumar and Russell, 1996).
79 Stroud et al. (2011) found that the accurate simulation of urban and large industrial plumes
80 required a grid resolution of 2.5 km in order to properly capture contributions from local
81 sources of primary organic aerosol (POA) and volatile organic compounds (VOCs).
82 Zakoura and Pandis (2019) investigated the effect of increasing grid resolution on PM_{2.5}
83 nitrate predictions and found that increasing the resolution to 4 km reduced bias by 65%.
84 Fountoukis et al. (2013) reported a reduction of the bias for black carbon (BC)
85 concentrations in the northeastern US when the grid resolution was reduced from 36x36
86 km to 4x4 km. Pan et al., (2017) allocated county-based emissions at 4 km and 1 km grid
87 resolution using the default approach from the National Emissions Inventory and found
88 small changes in model performance for NO_x and ozone. The 1 km simulation was able to
89 resolve the detailed spatial variability of emissions in heavily polluted areas including
90 highways, airports and industrially focused sub-regions.

91 One of the weaknesses of several of the above studies has been that the gridded
92 emissions used at the higher resolutions were the results of interpolation. It is not clear if
93 the remaining discrepancies between model predictions and measurements were due to
94 errors in the spatial distribution of the high-resolution emissions, errors in the overall
95 magnitude of the emissions over an urban area or other modeling errors in the simulation
96 of various processes (chemistry, condensation/evaporation, etc.). It is also not clear if errors
97 in previous simulations of urban PM_{2.5} are due to inaccuracies in the transport of regional
98 PM_{2.5} to urban areas. In this work, we explore the impacts of increasing the resolution of

99 emissions inputs and CTM output on PM_{2.5} predictions in southwestern Pennsylvania
100 during the months of February and July 2017, including the ability of the model to
101 reproduce observed differences between urban and rural PM_{2.5} at the various grid
102 resolutions.

103 Garcia Rivera et al. (2022) investigated the effects of increasing grid resolution of
104 model inputs and CTM output on source resolved predictions of PM_{2.5} concentration and
105 population exposure at 36 km, 12 km, 4 km, and 1 km. Moving to 12 x 12 km resolution
106 resolved much of the urban-rural gradient. Increasing to 4 x 4 km resolved stationary
107 sources such as power plants and the 1 x 1 km resolution results revealed intra-urban
108 variations and individual roadways. Regional pollutants with low spatial variability such
109 as PM_{2.5} nitrate showed modest changes when increasing the resolution to 4 x 4 km and
110 higher. Local pollutants such as black carbon and organic aerosol showed gradients that
111 were only resolved at the finest resolution. The ability of these simulations to reproduce
112 PM_{2.5} concentrations at different resolutions is evaluated here against multiple
113 measurement sources and types. The two months of February and July 2017 were chosen
114 to maximize the information gained with regard to the effects of seasonal variability of
115 major emissions sources and meteorology on predicted concentrations while keeping the
116 resources required for emissions inventory development at a feasible level.

117 We apply the Particulate Matter Comprehensive Air quality Model with Extensions
118 version 2.0 (PMCAMx-v2.0) to study the impact of increasing model resolution on the
119 ability to reproduce observed PM_{2.5} concentrations. We evaluate the PMCAMx predictions
120 at various grid resolutions against regulatory measurements of PM_{2.5} concentration and
121 composition, as well as measurements from a network of low-cost sensors (Zimmerman et
122 al., 2018) during February and July 2017 which provide a unique opportunity for
123 comparison not available to previous studies. Aerosol mass spectrometer (AMS)
124 measurements taken in Pittsburgh during February 2017 were also used to evaluate model
125 predictions.

126

127 **2 Model Description**

128 PMCAMx-v2.0, the Particulate Matter Comprehensive Air Quality Model with
129 Extensions (Karydis et al., 2010; Murphy and Pandis, 2010; Tsimpidi et al., 2010) is a

130 state-of-the-art atmospheric chemical transport model (CTM) that uses the framework of
131 the CAMx model (ENVIRON, 2005) with advanced aerosol chemistry modules. This
132 model uses detailed emissions and meteorology inputs to dynamically predict changes in
133 pollutant concentrations due to emission, transport, chemical reaction, removal processes,
134 and aerosol processes. To track the dynamic evolution of aerosol mass, 10 moving size
135 sections are used (Gaydos et al., 2003). The chemical mechanism SAPRC99 (Carter, 2000)
136 was used for gas-phase chemistry, including 237 individual chemical reactions involving
137 91 chemical species. Aqueous-phase chemistry is calculated with the Variable Size
138 Resolution Model (Fahey and Pandis, 2001). PMCAMx-v2.0 considers the formation of
139 aerosol mass comprised of sulfate, nitrate, ammonium, sodium, chloride, water, elemental
140 carbon, as well as lumped organic species (both primary and secondary). Inorganic aerosol
141 growth is modelled using an approach that assumes equilibrium between the bulk aerosol
142 and gas phases. Partitioning of semivolatile inorganic aerosol is calculated using
143 ISORROPIA-I (Nenes et al., 1998). The Volatility Basis Set (VBS) was used to calculate
144 partitioning of organic aerosol components across a distribution of species volatility
145 (Donahue et al., 2006). Volatility bins (10) with effective saturation concentration from 10^{-3}
146 3 to $10^6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (at 298 K) are used for primary organic aerosol (POA). Secondary organic
147 aerosol is split into anthropogenic (aSOA) and biogenic (bSOA) components, formed from
148 a variety of SOA-forming volatile organic compounds (VOCs) from human activity and
149 natural sources, respectively using NO_x -dependent SOA formation yields (Lane et al.,
150 2008). Both aSOA and bSOA are split into 4 volatility bins with effective saturation
151 concentration from 10^0 to $10^3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (at 298 K).

152

153 **3 Model Application**

154 Air quality simulations of a 5184 km² area comprised of southwestern Pennsylvania
155 and smaller parts of eastern Ohio and northern West Virginia were performed using
156 PMCAMx. Two distinct simulation periods of February and July 2017 were investigated.
157 The approach of Garcia et al. (2022) was used to produce speciated PM_{2.5} concentration
158 predictions at spatial resolution of 36 km, 12 km, 4 km, and 1 km. Surface-level boundary
159 conditions for the 36 x 36 km simulations are provided in Table S1.

160 Meteorological fields were calculated using the Weather Research and Forecasting
161 model (WRF-v3.6.1) with horizontal resolution of 12 x 12 km, providing wind
162 components, eddy diffusivity, temperature, pressure, humidity, clouds, and precipitation
163 inputs for use in PMCAMx. Meteorology initial and boundary conditions were retrieved
164 from the ERA-Interim global climate re-analysis database. The United States Geological
165 Survey database was used to obtain input data for terrain, land-use, and soil type. When
166 necessary, WRF output was interpolated to higher resolutions. An evaluation of
167 interpolated meteorological inputs using data from METAR stations near the city of
168 Pittsburgh in southwestern Pennsylvania determined that errors in the magnitude and
169 phasing of diurnal cycles of temperature, relative humidity, and wind speed are
170 appropriately small for use in air quality studies. These results are provided in the
171 supplementary material (Fig. S1, S2).

172 Anthropogenic emissions are derived from the 2017 projections of the 2011
173 National Emissions Inventory (Eyth and Vukovich, 2015) modelling platform. The Sparse
174 Matrix Operator Kernel Emissions modeling system (SMOKE) was used, along with
175 meteorological inputs to calculate emissions at a horizontal resolution of 12 x 12 km.
176 Default spatial surrogates were used to allocate these emissions to higher resolutions.
177 Custom surrogates were developed for commercial cooking and on-road traffic emissions
178 sectors within the 1 x 1 km grid and used for the primary analysis in this work. The use of
179 these new surrogates results in different spatial distribution of emissions for cooking and
180 on-road traffic sources than what would be observed with the default spatial surrogates.
181 Additional simulations were performed to quantify the impact of these proposed surrogates
182 on predicted PM_{2.5} concentrations.

183 For commercial cooking, the normalized restaurant count was used to distribute the
184 emissions from the sector in space within the 1 x 1 km domain. This surrogate distributed
185 commercial cooking emissions based on the density of restaurants identified by the Google
186 Places Application Programming Interface. To allocate on-road traffic emissions, the
187 output from the traffic model of Ma et al. (2020) was used. This model simulates hourly
188 traffic using data from the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. Emissions from the
189 on-road traffic sector were then allocated based on these values.

190 Model predictions of sulfate, nitrate, elemental carbon and organic aerosol were
191 compared with measurements from 4 sites from the EPA Chemical Speciation Network
192 (EPA-CSN) (U.S. EPA, 2002). The locations of these 4 sites are shown in Figure 1a. These
193 sites include: Lawrenceville, an urban background site 4 km northeast of downtown
194 Pittsburgh; Hillman State Park located in a state park in southwest Pennsylvania in a rural
195 and remote location approximately 40 km upwind of Pittsburgh; Steubenville in the Ohio
196 River Valley close to industrial installations and coal-fired power plants, and the Liberty-
197 Clairton monitor, which is located close to the Clairton Coke Works in the Monongahela
198 River Valley 14 km southeast of downtown Pittsburgh. Speciated PM_{2.5} measurements
199 from EPA-CSN sites are available every three days during the simulation periods. Daily
200 non-speciated measurements of total PM_{2.5} mass concentration are available from 17 sites
201 within the inner simulation domain and are used to further evaluate total PM_{2.5} mass
202 concentration predictions. The locations of these sites are also shown in Figure 1a.

203 For February 2017, high-resolution AMS measurements from the Carnegie Mellon
204 University supersite (Gu et al., 2018) are used to evaluate the predicted chemical
205 composition of PM_{2.5} model predictions. Positive matrix factorization results are also used
206 to investigate the breakdown of organic aerosol components. AMS measurements were
207 taken continuously from February 1 to February 14, 2017. Due to uncertainties with the
208 AMS collection efficiency during this campaign, we use here only the fractional particle
209 composition data.

210 PMCAMx predictions of PM_{2.5} were also compared with measurements taken with
211 a network of Real-time Affordable Multi-Pollutant (RAMP) monitors (Zimmerman et al.,
212 2018) distributed in the city of Pittsburgh. During the winter period measurements at 7 sites
213 were available, all located within the boundaries of the city of Pittsburgh, while 22 sites
214 were in operation during the summer period with a few sites also outside the city (Fig. 1b).
215 Uncertainty in these low-cost measurements of PM_{2.5} mass concentration is between 3-4
216 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ for hourly averaging times (Malings et al., 2019).

217 The model performance is assessed in terms of the mean bias (BIAS), the mean
218 error (ERROR), the fractional bias (FBIAS) and the fractional error (ERROR):

$$219 \quad \text{BIAS} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N P_i - O_i \quad (1)$$

$$220 \quad \text{FBIAS} = \frac{2}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{P_i - O_i}{P_i + O_i} \quad (2)$$

$$221 \quad \text{ERROR} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |P_i - O_i| \quad (3)$$

$$223 \quad \text{FERROR} = \frac{2}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{|P_i - O_i|}{P_i + O_i} \quad (4)$$

222

224 where N is the number of valid measurements, P_i is the predicted concentration and O_i is
 225 the corresponding observed concentration. The fractional error metric is bounded by 0
 226 (perfect prediction performance) and 2.0 (extremely poor prediction performance).
 227 Fractional bias is bounded by -2.0 (extreme underprediction) and +2.0 (extreme
 228 overprediction).

229

230 **4 Evaluation of high-resolution model performance**

231 **4.1 Winter**

232 Table 1 summarizes the performance metrics of daily average PMCAMx-v2.0
 233 PM_{2.5} predictions in the 1x1 km resolution, when compared with daily measurements from
 234 EPA regulatory PM_{2.5} monitors. The speciated performance is illustrated in Figure 2.
 235 Predictions of total PM_{2.5} mass perform well against regulatory measurements in the
 236 February simulation period, with fractional error of 0.3 and fractional bias of +0.07.

237 Average measured PM_{2.5} sulfate for this time period was 1.9 μg m⁻³. Lower sulfate
 238 levels were observed at the Lawrenceville site in Pittsburgh (1.2 μg m⁻³) while significantly
 239 higher levels were observed at the Steubenville site (3.1 μg m⁻³). Predicted domain-average
 240 PM_{2.5} sulfate at 1 x 1 km resolution was 1.3 μg m⁻³. Overall fractional error for sulfate
 241 predictions was 0.41 and no overall bias was observed (fractional bias of -0.02). PM_{2.5}
 242 sulfate was slightly overpredicted at Hillman State Park (+0.18 fractional bias) and
 243 Lawrenceville (+0.25 fractional bias) and underpredicted at the industrial sites,
 244 Steubenville (-0.24 fractional bias) and Liberty/Clairton (-0.43 fractional bias) where
 245 observed PM_{2.5} sulfate concentrations were higher.

246 Overpredictions were seen for PM_{2.5} nitrate, with a fractional bias of +0.81. The
247 average measured concentration at EPA-CSN sites within the simulation domain was 1.5
248 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, while the domain-average predicted concentration was 1.8 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. Observed
249 average PM_{2.5} nitrate concentrations at Hillman State Park and Lawrenceville were slightly
250 lower at 1.1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and 1.2 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively. Nitrate at the Steubenville location was
251 observed to be higher on average at 2.2 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. This overprediction is seen at all sites but
252 is particularly prevalent at Hillman State Park, Lawrenceville, and Liberty/Clairton, where
253 errors are of the order of a factor of two. Previous PMCAMx modeling studies have found
254 similar over-predictions. Part of this overprediction was due to the use of coarse-grid
255 resolution (Zakoura and Pandis, 2018), but this is unlikely to be the cause here, because
256 81% of the predicted domain-average nitrate is transported from outside of the inner
257 modeling domain. These inconsistencies in PM_{2.5} nitrate predictions are likely due to errors
258 in the partitioning of nitrate between the fine (PM_{2.5}) and coarse (PM₁₀) modes, resulting
259 in an overprediction of PM_{2.5} nitrate. Resolving this modeling error likely requires
260 improvements to the treatment of dust within the model, and the use of a dynamic approach
261 for inorganic aerosol calculations rather than the bulk equilibrium approach.

262 The behavior of PM_{2.5} ammonium measurements is similar to that of nitrate as most
263 of it is in the form of ammonium nitrate. The average measured concentration at the four
264 EPA-CSN stations was 0.9 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. At Hillman State Park and Lawrenceville, the measured
265 average was lower at 0.5 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ but higher at the Liberty/Clairton location at 2.1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$.
266 PM_{2.5} ammonium was overpredicted similarly to PM_{2.5} nitrate with +0.83 fractional bias.
267 The average measured concentration of PM_{2.5} elemental carbon at EPA-CSN sites during
268 February 2017 was 1.1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. Elemental carbon concentrations are more localized than
269 the inorganic PM_{2.5} components. At Hillman State Park the average measured
270 concentration was only 0.5 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ while at Liberty/Clairton the averaged measured
271 concentration was 2.9 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. For elemental carbon, the predicted domain-average was 0.4
272 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. Average elemental carbon concentration in the 4 x 4 km simulation grid outside of
273 the inner modeling domain was 0.3 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. Black carbon predictions at all sites had a
274 fractional error of 0.71 with fractional bias of -0.08. Elemental carbon was overpredicted
275 at the urban site with fractional bias of 0.73 and underpredicted at the other sites.

276 Average measured OA during this period was $4.4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, but with significant
277 spatial variability. At Hillman State Park and Lawrenceville measured OA was $3.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
278 and $3.4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively. At Liberty/Clairton and Steubenville the average measured
279 OA was $7 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and $6.3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively. Domain-average predicted OA was $2.2 \mu\text{g}$
280 m^{-3} . Outside of the inner 1 x 1 km domain, average predicted OA was $1.6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$,
281 suggesting that the majority of predicted OA is transported from outside of the 1 x 1 km
282 grid. Overall OA prediction performance in the winter is acceptable at 0.53 fractional error
283 and low fractional bias (-0.01). At individual sites, performance varies. OA is predicted
284 with low fractional bias (-0.10) at the rural Hillman State Park site. OA is overpredicted by
285 with +0.31 fractional bias at the urban site in Lawrenceville and underpredicted at both
286 industrial sites. An added degree of uncertainty exists with the industrial sites within the
287 inner domain. The emissions from these sources may be underestimated in the inventory
288 and these locations are also difficult to accurately model due to their geographic location
289 in river valleys.

290 Average concentrations of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ sulfate, nitrate, and ammonium in the 4 x 4 km
291 resolution domain were around 83% of the average predicted concentrations in the inner 1
292 x 1 km simulation grid. For elemental carbon and OA, the outer concentration was 64%
293 and 73% of the inner concentration respectively, indicating that these species had
294 significant local sources. For these more local pollutants, the model appears to perform
295 well in terms of capturing urban-rural gradients, but with a tendency towards
296 underprediction at the rural site in Hillman State Park and overprediction at the urban site
297 in Lawrenceville. The model also underpredicts EC and OA at the industrial locations,
298 especially elemental carbon (-0.67 and -1.02 fractional bias at Steubenville and
299 Liberty/Clairton, respectively). This again suggests errors in the emissions inventory or
300 problems in simulating atmospheric dispersion near the sources.

301 Comparisons with the PM_1 composition as determined by the AMS from February
302 3 through February 14, 2017, show excellent agreement for all species (Fig. 3a). Gu et al.
303 (2018) used PMF analysis and allocated total measured OA into five factors. Three of them
304 corresponded to primary organic aerosol: hydrocarbon-like OA (HOA), cooking OA
305 (COA) and biomass burning OA (BBOA) and two secondary OA factors: more-oxidized
306 organic aerosol (MO-OOA) and less-oxidized organic aerosol (LO-OOA). To compare

307 PMCAMx predictions with the primary PMF factors, two additional simulations were
308 performed in which emissions from biomass burning and commercial cooking were set to
309 zero. The predicted concentrations were then subtracted from the base case to estimate the
310 contribution from each respective source. The remaining primary OA was assigned to
311 HOA. The LO-OOA and MO-OOA factors were added together and compared with the
312 PMCAMx SOA predictions.

313 The predicted cooking OA (COA) at the CMU site is 25% of the total OA and is in
314 agreement with the PMF/AMS estimate of 22% (Fig. 3b). This is encouraging given the
315 small bias of the model for total OA levels. The predicted HOA and BBOA are higher than
316 measured by a factor of 2 or more. At the same time, the measurements indicate a
317 surprisingly high contribution of SOA (53% of the total OA) during a period with little
318 photochemical activity and low levels of OH radicals. SOA is predicted to be just 20% of
319 the total during this time period. These discrepancies may indicate transformation of the
320 HOA and BBOA to OOA during this wintertime period, that are not included in the model.
321 Kodros et al. (2020) recently suggested that BBOA can react with the NO_3 radical during
322 the winter and can be transformed to OOA.

323

324 **4.2 Summer**

325 Total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass concentrations are underpredicted in the summer period. The
326 average measured $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ value in the regulatory network in the area was $11.4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, while
327 the average predicted value at the regulatory sites was $4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ lower.

328 Speciated $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ performance is illustrated in Figure 4. Average measured $\text{PM}_{2.5}$
329 sulfate for the summer period was $2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. Slightly lower levels were observed at the
330 Lawrenceville site in Pittsburgh ($1.9 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). Liberty/Clairton had higher measured sulfate
331 concentrations ($2.6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), but this difference between locations is lower than what was
332 observed in the winter period. Predicted domain-average $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ sulfate at $1 \times 1 \text{ km}$
333 resolution was $1.3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. Overall fractional error (0.62) and fractional bias (-0.21) for
334 sulfate predictions was higher than in the winter simulation period. $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ sulfate was
335 underpredicted at all sites but to the largest extent at Hillman State Park (-0.36 fractional
336 error).

337 Overpredictions of PM_{2.5} nitrate were also seen in the summer period, and at all
338 types of sites. Average measured PM_{2.5} nitrate was 0.3 µg m⁻³, much lower than in the
339 winter. The domain-average predicted PM_{2.5} nitrate was 0.7 µg m⁻³. Again, predicted PM_{2.5}
340 nitrate in the inner domain is dominated by material transported from outside the
341 boundaries (75%), so the issue is not resolved by using a high-resolution grid.
342 Improvements to PM_{2.5} nitrate formation are needed in the form of dust models with
343 increased complexity to resolve the issues with fine-coarse mode partitioning of particulate
344 nitrate. These issues have been highlighted by decreased concentrations of PM_{2.5} pollution
345 in recent years.

346 Observed PM_{2.5} ammonium concentrations at EPA-CSN sites were also much
347 lower in the summer with an average value of 0.5 µg m⁻³. Slightly higher average
348 concentrations were observed at Liberty/Clairton (0.7 µg m⁻³) and slightly lower
349 concentrations were observed at Steubenville (0.4 µg m⁻³). The domain-average predicted
350 PM_{2.5} ammonium concentration was 0.6 µg m⁻³. The average concentration directly outside
351 of the inner domain was 0.5 µg m⁻³. Overall performance was better for ammonium in the
352 summer than in the winter with fractional error of 0.62 and fractional bias of +0.44. The
353 strongest overprediction is seen at the Steubenville site (+0.57 fractional bias).

354 The average measured elemental carbon (EC) concentration in July was 0.7 µg
355 m⁻³. Measured EC carbon was significantly higher at Liberty/Clairton (1 µg m⁻³) and lower
356 at rural Hillman State Park (0.4 µg m⁻³). Domain-average predicted EC was 0.3 µg m⁻³.
357 Outside of the inner domain, the average predicted concentration was 0.2 µg m⁻³. Elemental
358 carbon predictions in July had a lower fractional error compared to the winter at 0.60 but
359 showed a stronger negative fractional bias at -0.33. The model severely underpredicts at
360 Hillman State Park (-0.86 fractional bias), where measured concentrations were lowest, but
361 also at the industrial sites of Steubenville (-0.55 fractional bias) and Liberty/Clairton (-0.65
362 fractional bias). EC was slightly overpredicted at the urban Lawrenceville location (+0.14
363 fractional bias). While the urban-rural gradient in EC is slightly overpredicted, the model
364 is still able to capture well the variability between rural (Hillman State Park) and urban
365 (Lawrenceville). The model struggles to reproduce high measurements of EC at the
366 Steubenville site, reiterating the issues with industrial EC seen in the winter.

367 Average measured OA concentration was $4.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in July. Higher concentrations
368 were observed at the industrial sites, Liberty/Clairton and Steubenville ($5.0 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)
369 respectively. The lowest observed concentration was in Hillman State Park ($3.6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$).
370 The average predicted concentration at CSN sites was $2.7 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. On average, OA is
371 underpredicted with fractional bias of -0.47. This underprediction occurs at all sites but is
372 less prevalent at the urban Lawrenceville location (-0.19 fractional bias) and is most
373 dramatic in Steubenville (-0.65 fractional bias). Because such a large fraction of the OA in
374 the summer is predicted to be secondary (50% of local OA on average) and transported
375 from outside of the inner modeling domain (84% of total OA), treatment of SOA formation
376 is likely a key factor contributing to the underprediction of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ in the summer. While
377 these improvements are necessary for overall model improvement, they do not have
378 significant impact on the urban-rural gradients which are the focus of this work and are
379 driven by primary species. The performance of EC predictions in various locations is
380 encouraging with regard to primary $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ performance.

381

382 **5 Effect of grid resolution on $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ performance**

383 To determine the effect of grid resolution on the ability of the model to resolve
384 geographical variations in $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations, daily average measurements from the 17
385 EPA regulatory sites were compared with PMCAMx predictions from simulations at 36
386 km, 12 km, 4 km and 1 km. The PMCAMx performance metrics are summarized in Table
387 2.

388

389 **5.1 Winter**

390 During the winter period, increasing grid resolution reduces the average fractional
391 error from 34% at 36 x 36 km to 30% at 1 x 1 km. The higher resolution also improved the
392 fractional bias, from -0.09 at 36 x 36 km to +0.05 at 1 x 1 km. The performance is illustrated
393 in Figure 5. Performance at urban locations stayed steady in the winter, with fractional
394 error changing from 0.30 to 0.26 and fractional bias changing from +0.02 to +0.08 moving
395 from 36 km to 1 km resolution (Fig. S3). Rural performance improved to a greater extent,
396 with fractional error improving from 0.33 to 0.28 and fractional bias lowering from +0.21
397 to +0.11.

398 The comparison with low-cost sensor measurements largely represents the
399 performance of the model in terms of urban PM_{2.5} predictions. The performance metrics of
400 PMCAMx-v2.0 when compared to measurements from low-cost sensors are shown in
401 Table 3. Moving from low to high resolution, the predictions go from no bias (-0.02) to a
402 bias of +0.24. Due to the slight overprediction of the urban-rural gradient seen earlier
403 (particularly with EC), the high resolution would likely lead to more positive biases when
404 compared to a largely urban network. Fractional error increases slightly, but still exhibits
405 good performance moving from 0.33 to 0.37.

406

407 **5.2 Summer**

408 In the summer period, (Fig. 6) the model performance improved as the resolution
409 increased from 36 km to 1 km. Fractional error decreased from 0.53 to 0.48, while
410 fractional bias increased from -0.46 to -0.39. In July, performance at the urban locations
411 significantly increased with resolution (Fig. S4). Fractional error decreased from 52% at
412 36 x 36 km to 0.42 at 1 x 1 km. Fractional bias also improved from -0.46 at the coarse grid
413 resolution to -0.39 at the finest scale. Rural predictions of PM_{2.5} were also better with
414 increasing resolution in the summer. Fractional error decreased from 0.31 to 0.22 while
415 fractional bias decreased from +0.05 to -0.05.

416 Larger improvements are seen with increasing resolution during the summer when
417 compared to measurements from low-cost sensors. Starting from a large negative bias of
418 $-5.4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (fractional bias of -0.48) at the 36 x 36 km resolution, performance consistently
419 improved with each increasing resolution step with the bias eventually reaching $-3.7 \mu\text{g}$
420 m^{-3} (fractional bias of -0.27) at the 1 x 1 km. There was also a reduction in fractional error
421 from 0.52 at the coarse to 0.41 at the fine 1 x 1 km resolution. These metrics are
422 encouraging, although they are likely impacted by an overprediction of the urban-rural
423 gradient, similar to winter. Improvement of the secondary PM_{2.5} predictions is still the
424 largest source of error between predictions and this source of measurements.

425

426 **6 Evaluation of Novel Emissions Surrogates**

427 For commercial cooking, the normalized restaurant count was used to distribute the
428 emissions from the sector in space within the 1 x 1 km domain. Geographical information

429 was collected for all restaurant locations in the inner domain from the Google Places
430 Application Programming Interface. This includes southwestern Pennsylvania as well as
431 parts of eastern Ohio and northern West Virginia. To allocate on-road traffic emissions, the
432 output from the traffic model of Ma et al. (2020) was used. This model simulated hourly
433 traffic using data from the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation sites located
434 throughout the inner modeling domain. The use of new surrogates resulted in a new spatial
435 distribution of emissions for both cooking and onroad traffic sources when compared to
436 those developed using default emissions surrogates. The changes in spatial distributions
437 are illustrated in the supplementary material (Figures S5, S6, S7, and S8). These novel
438 emissions surrogates resulted in larger emissions of both traffic and cooking in the
439 downtown area. In the case of on-road traffic, major highways in the inner domain are
440 emphasized with the new surrogates.

441 For both February and July 2017, the largest observed change when using the novel
442 surrogates is an increase in predicted $PM_{2.5}$ of around $3 \mu g m^{-3}$ in the downtown Pittsburgh
443 area (Fig. 7). Differences in predicted $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations outside of the urban areas of
444 the inner domain are very small (less than $0.5 \mu g m^{-3}$ in magnitude).

445 Model performance at 1 x 1 km resolution is detailed in Table 4. Negligible changes
446 in performance were seen using EPA regulatory $PM_{2.5}$ data in February 2017. Small
447 improvements were seen at regulatory sites in July 2017, where fractional error was
448 reduced from 51% to 48% and fractional bias increased from -43% to -39%. A positive
449 shift in fractional bias was seen with the use of the new surrogates during both periods
450 when compared to low-cost sensor measurements, resulting in a modest overprediction of
451 $PM_{2.5}$ in the winter (+0.24 fractional bias) and a modest underprediction of $PM_{2.5}$ in the
452 summer (-0.27 fractional bias). The larger changes when compared to the low-cost sensor
453 measurements are a result of the location of the low-cost sensors in urban areas, where the
454 new surrogates predicted elevated $PM_{2.5}$ mass concentrations.

455 **7 Conclusions**

456 We applied PMCAMx-v2.0 over southwestern Pennsylvania during February and
457 July 2017 at grid resolutions of 36 km, 12 km, 4 km and 1 km. Emissions were calculated
458 for the relevant grids by using the spatial surrogates provided along with the 2011 NEI for

459 all emissions sectors except traffic and cooking, for which 1 x 1 km spatial surrogates were
460 developed.

461 PMCAMx predicts winter sulfate, elemental carbon and organic aerosol
462 concentrations with fractional biases below 10% at high resolution. Nitrate concentrations
463 are overpredicted (bias +1.4 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) following the trend of previous studies in both the US
464 and Europe. Agreement with total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ measurements is also encouraging with a
465 fractional bias of +5%. Variability between urban and rural predictions of local pollutants
466 EC and organic aerosol (OA) are reproduced well in the winter period. Underpredictions
467 of summer OA concentrations led to underpredictions of total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass. Summer sulfate
468 is reproduced with fractional bias of -21% and elemental carbon (EC) is predicted with
469 fractional bias of -33%. Nitrate is similarly overpredicted in the summer with fractional
470 bias of +70% although with a much smaller magnitude than in the winter (+0.4 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$).
471 Differences between urban and rural EC is also predicted well in the summer, while OA is
472 predicted to vary little between urban and rural locations. This is indicative of a greater
473 contribution of secondary species to OA during this period.

474 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ prediction performance improved in almost all cases when increasing
475 the resolution from 36 km to 1 km. Underpredictions at urban sites and overpredictions at
476 rural sites were reduced at the same time. This is true when comparing against
477 measurements from regulatory sites as well as low-cost monitors. The improved
478 performance here is evidence of the enhanced ability of the model to capture important
479 urban-rural gradients in $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ pollution by increasing the resolution of predictions to 1 x 1
480 km. Increasing resolution of predictions has been shown here to improve model
481 performance when comparing predicted $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations with observations from
482 regulatory monitors and low-cost sensors. However, these simulations highlight the need
483 for specific improvements to some of the secondary $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ formation pathways in the
484 model. Improvement of the treatment of dust in the model is required to better model the
485 distribution of particulate nitrate between $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} modes. Additionally,
486 improvements to SOA formation chemistry within the model, particularly from biogenic
487 sources outside of the inner modeling domain, will likely have a significant impact on
488 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ predictions around the city of Pittsburgh.

489

490

491 *Code Availability.* The PMCAMx-v2.0 code is available in Zenodo at
492 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6772851> (Dinkelacker et al., 2022). License (for files):
493 GNU General Public License v3.0.

494

495 *Author contributions.* BTD performed the PMCAMx simulations, analyzed the results, and
496 wrote the manuscript. PGR wrote the code for data analysis, prepared anthropogenic
497 emissions and other inputs for the PMCAMx simulations, and assisted in writing the
498 manuscript. IK set up the WRF simulations and assisted in the preparation of the
499 meteorological inputs. SNP and PJA designed and coordinated the study and helped in the
500 writing of the paper. All authors reviewed and commented on the manuscript.

501

502 *Competing Interests.* The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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617 **Table 1.** Comparison of daily average high-resolution PMCAMx-v2.0 predictions with
 618 daily EPA-CSN measurements during February and July 2017.
 619

February 2017						
	Sulfate	Nitrate	Ammon.	Elemental Carbon	Organic Aerosol	PM_{2.5}^a
Measured Avg. ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	1.92	1.51	0.91	1.08	4.37	10.34
Predicted Avg. ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	1.70	2.90	1.62	0.94	3.68	10.52
Error ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	0.79	1.54	1.03	0.78	2.15	3.02
Fractional Error	0.41	0.83	0.96	0.71	0.53	0.30
Bias ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	-0.22	1.40	0.71	-0.14	-0.68	0.18
Fractional Bias	-0.02	0.81	0.83	-0.08	-0.01	0.05
July 2017						
	Sulfate	Nitrate	Ammon.	Elemental Carbon	Organic Aerosol	PM_{2.5}^a
Measured Avg. ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	2.04	0.26	0.53	0.74	4.46	11.24
Predicted Avg. ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	1.60	0.68	0.79	0.56	2.67	7.26
Error ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	1.12	0.45	0.39	0.39	2.46	4.67
Fractional Error	0.62	0.82	0.62	0.60	0.67	0.49
Bias ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	-0.44	0.42	0.26	-0.18	-1.85	-4.01
Fractional Bias	-0.21	0.70	0.44	-0.33	-0.47	-0.39

621 ^a Measurements from the regulatory EPA monitors.

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623 **Table 2.** Comparison of daily average PMCAMx-v2.0 predicted PM_{2.5} concentrations
 624 during February and July 2017 with daily measurements from 17 EPA regulatory
 625 monitors.
 626

	36 x 36 km	12 x 12 km	4 x 4 km	1 x 1 km
February 2017				
Measured Avg. ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	10.34	10.34	10.34	10.34
Predicted Avg. ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	9.78	9.68	10.49	10.52
Error ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	3.35	3.16	3.04	3.02
Fractional Error	0.34	0.32	0.30	0.30
Bias ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	-0.56	-0.66	0.15	0.18
Fractional Bias	-0.09	-0.10	0.06	0.05
July 2017				
Measured Avg. ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	11.24	11.24	11.24	11.24
Predicted Avg. ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	6.90	6.86	7.26	7.23
Error ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	4.89	5.05	4.67	4.65
Fractional Error	0.53	0.53	0.49	0.48
Bias ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	-4.34	-4.39	-3.98	-4.01
Fractional Bias	-0.45	-0.47	-0.39	-0.39

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628 **Table 3.** Comparison of daily average PMCAMx-v2.0 predicted PM_{2.5} concentrations
 629 during February and July 2017 with daily low-cost sensor (RAMP) measurements.
 630

	36 x 36 km	12 x 12 km	4 x 4 km	1 x 1 km
February 2017				
Measured Avg. ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	11.65	11.65	11.65	11.65
Predicted Avg. ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	10.23	11.64	12.04	13.50
Error ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	4.53	4.53	4.51	5.12
Fractional Error	0.33	0.33	0.34	0.37
Bias ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	-1.43	-0.02	0.4	1.85
Fractional Bias	-0.02	<0.01	0.14	0.24
July 2017				
Measured Avg. ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	12.59	12.59	12.59	12.59
Predicted Avg. ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	7.19	7.44	8.06	8.83
Error ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	5.60	5.70	5.29	4.89
Fractional Error	0.51	0.51	0.46	0.42
Bias ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	-5.40	-5.15	-4.53	-3.76
Fractional Bias	-0.48	-0.43	-0.36	-0.27

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633 **Table 4.** Performance of daily average predicted total PM_{2.5} concentrations compared to
 634 daily measurements from regulatory sites and low-cost sensors with the use of old
 635 surrogates and new surrogates for on-road traffic and commercial cooking within the 1 x
 636 1 km resolution grid.
 637

February 2017				
	Old Surrogates		New Surrogates	
	Regulatory network	Low-cost sensors	Regulatory network	Low-cost sensors
Observed Average ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	10.34	11.65	10.34	11.65
Predicted Average ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	10.23	11.32	10.52	13.50
Error ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	2.94	4.12	3.02	5.12
Fractional Error	0.29	0.31	0.30	0.37
Bias ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	-0.11	-0.33	0.18	1.85
Fractional Bias	-0.04	0.08	0.05	0.24

July 2017				
	Old Surrogates		New Surrogates	
	Regulatory network	Low-cost sensors	Regulatory network	Low-cost sensors
Observed Average ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	11.24	12.58	11.24	12.58
Predicted Average ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	7.09	7.98	7.26	8.83
Error ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	4.91	5.32	4.67	4.89
Fractional Error	0.51	0.47	0.49	0.42
Bias ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	-4.33	-4.61	-4.01	-3.76
Fractional Bias	-0.43	-0.37	-0.39	-0.27

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Figure 1. Monitoring sites. (a) Particulate matter speciation measurement sites from EPA-CSN and PM_{2.5} regulatory monitors. The entire inner modeling domain is shown. (b) low-cost sensor sites. City of Pittsburgh boundaries are shown in both panels for reference.

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Figure 2. Comparison of daily average PMCAMx-v2.0 predicted concentrations of PM_{2.5} (a) sulfate, (b) nitrate, (c) ammonium, (d) elemental carbon, and (e) organic aerosol with daily measurements from EPA-CSN sites during February 2017.

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654 **Figure 3.** (a) Comparison of PMCAMx-v2.0 predicted composition of PM₁ with the
655 corresponding AMS measurements at the CMU site and (b) organic aerosol composition
656 based on the PMF analysis of the AMS measurements and predicted composition.

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Figure 4. Comparison of PMCAMx-v2.0 predicted concentrations of PM_{2.5} (a) sulfate, (b) nitrate, (c) ammonium, (d) elemental carbon, and (e) organic aerosol with measurements from EPA-CSN sites during July 2017.

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665 **Figure 5.** Comparison of daily average PMCAMx-v2.0 predicted concentrations of PM_{2.5}

666 with daily regulatory measurements and daily low-cost sensor measurements at (a) 36 x

667 36, (b) 12 x 12, (c) 4 x 4, and (d) 1 x 1 km during February 2017.

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672 **Figure 6.** Comparison of daily average PMCAMx-v2.0 predicted concentrations of $PM_{2.5}$
 673 with daily regulatory measurements and daily low-cost sensor measurements at (a) 36 x
 674 36, (b) 12 x 12, (c) 4 x 4, and (d) 1 x 1 km during July 2017.

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Figure 7. Difference between predicted monthly average $PM_{2.5}$ mass concentration when using novel surrogates and original surrogates in (a) February 2017 and (b) July 2017 for the 1 x 1 km resolution simulation grid. A positive value indicates a higher concentration predicted with the novel surrogates.